

Deliverable Phase 1 – Climate risk assessment

Advanced Risk assessment for ClimAte resilience Debates,

Innovations and Actions in Dobrich (ARCADIA)

Bulgaria, Dobrich

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1. Document Information

Deliverable Title	Phase 1 – Climate risk assessment
Brief Description	The report on the application and adaptation of the CLIMAAX framework as first deliverable contains relevant data utilizing high-resolution datasets and other key resources suggested by the CLIMAAX handbook and as well as guidelines for further refining and local application of the framework in Dobrich municipality. The report also encompasses the initial process of scoping to define the objectives (desired results of the analysis), the local context for Dobrich and identify the stakeholders.
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5. Abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation / acronym	Description
ASPFR	Area of Significant Potential for Flood Risk
CRA	Climate Risk Assessment
DRRP	Disaster Risk Reduction Program
IDP	Integrated Development Plan
NIMH	National Institute of Meteorology and Hydrology

6. Executive summary

Motivation

This report presents the results of the first phase of the climate risk assessment in the Dobrich municipality, focused on flood hazards. The main objective of the analysis is to provide a scientifically sound risk assessment and to serve as a basis for future flood adaptation and management strategies as well as to serve as a pilot analysis for the other climate hazards.

Main results

The provided flood maps with different recurrence intervals (10, 50, 100 and 500 years) allowed the identification of the endangered areas. The data show that the areas with the highest risk are located along the Dobrich River and in the lowest parts of the city, where a high concentration of residential, commercial and industrial buildings is observed.

The results of the study reveal an exponential increase in the potential economic damage and the number of affected population with an increase in the flood recurrence period. According to preliminary calculations, in a 500-year flood, the financial losses reach 100 million. EUR, and over 12,000 people would be at risk.

Among the main challenges to be addressed are the assessment of the socio-economic consequences of the floods, the analysis of the vulnerability of different social groups, a more precise assessment of economic damages (taking into account insurance premiums), providing the study with hydrometeorological information, and developing specific adaptation measures.

This assessment will be used to inform and impact the broader framework of the climate strategies of the Dobrich municipality and will serve as the basis for the future update relevant climate policies like the Disaster Risk Reduction Program (DRRP). The conclusions and recommendations of this report will ensure more informed and scientifically based decision-making for management of climate risks in the territory of the municipality (and the neighboring municipalities). In this process, more stakeholders should be involved, especially from the businesses and population affected by the climate hazards.

Conclusion

The flood risk assessment in the Dobrich municipality reveals significant challenges to the urban resilience in the conditions of a changing climate. Among the challenges remain the analyses of the vulnerability of different social groups, the economic damages in the different levels of threat zones, the development of specific adaptation measures. The results emphasize the need to combine engineering solutions with nature-based measures and increase the awareness of the population for effective flood risk management.

The report will contribute to building knowledge and awareness in the Dobrich municipality to prepare and adopt transformational adaptation strategies that build resilience by supporting the advancement and implementation of climate risk assessments. Not least, putting the participatory processes central to the process of climate risk assessment and following policy actions, the project will continue to reach out to the relevant local, regional and national stakeholders.

1 Introduction

Figure 1-1. Location of Dobrich-

Figure 1-2. Land cover types of Dobrich Municipality

Figure 1-3. Climatogram of Dobrich Municipality

1.1 Background

Location of Dobrich Municipality

Dobrich Municipality, situated in Bulgaria's Northeast Planning Region (NUTS2), covers 109.018 km² (Figure 1-1). It is the smallest municipality in Dobrich District (NUTS3).

Relief and land-cover of Dobrich City Municipality

The relief of Dobrich Municipality is flat to slightly rolling. It is part of the Dobrudzha plateau and ranges from 191 to 350 m above sea level. The northern parts of the municipality are lower in elevation than the southern periphery. This topographical gradient influences the flow of the Dobrichka River and its tributaries. The municipal territory is a mosaic of diverse land cover types: densely built-up zones with predominant impermeable surfaces in the central area, a more scattered structure with integrated green spaces in residential districts, and significant green areas along the river course and in peripheral zones (Figure 1-2).

Climatic Characteristics of Dobrich City Municipality

The municipality's climate is moderate continental (Figure 1-3). The annual temperature is 10.2°C, with slight variations throughout the years. July is warmer, with an average temperature of 21.1 °C (Table 1). The highest temperature varies between 2.5 °C in January and 28.3 °C in August. The highest recorded temperature is 39.1 °C. The monthly minimum is in January (Table 1-1). The lowest temperature is between -0.2 °C and -43.8°C. The number of sunshine hours in

Dobrich Municipality varies from approximately five hours during winter to around 12 hours during June and July.

Table 1-1
Temperature (T, °C) of Dobrich Municipality

T °C	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XII
T _{av}	-1.6	0.1	3.6	9.5	14.8	18.6	21.1	20.7	16.6	11.4	6.5	2.5
T _{max}	-2.8	-1.5	1.8	5.9	10.9	15.4	17.7	17.7	13.5	8.5	4.6	-0.7
T _{min}	2.5	4.9	9.2	15.9	21.4	25.4	28.3	28.2	24.3	17.8	11.2	5.3
T _{max. absolutely}	17	20.6	27.1	31.5	36.5	34	37.1	39.1	39.1	33.8	28.3	19.3
T _{min absolutely}	-22.7	-21.2	-18.3	-43.8	0	4.5	7.2	7.5	-0.2	-3.6	-14.3	-17.9
Sunshine hours (n)	88	86	81	77	78	75	69	70	74	79	86	87

Precipitation is notably scarce, with an annual average of around 540 mm. Rainfall dominates in June and May and is lowest in autumn (Table 1-2). The maximum daily rainfall (mm) with various probabilities is 80,96 mm with 0.5% probability, 153,64 with 1.0% probability, and 205,16 with 0.1% probability. Snow cover is up to 2.5 months. Atmospheric conditions are marked by high humidity, averaging 78%, with winter humidity reaching 85-86% and summer humidity dropping to 68-69%. The dominant wind is northwestern, with a maximum speed of 20 m/s.

Table 1-2
Precipitation (P, mm) and wind (m/s) of Dobrich Municipality

P, mm	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XII
Relative Humidity, %	88	86	81	77	78	75	69	70	74	79	86	87
Precipitation	40	35	35	46	51	56	47	39	42	39	55	52
Number days with precipitation	6	5	7	8	8	9	7	5	5	5	5	6
Wind (m/s)	4,8	5,0	5,1	4,3	3,5	2,9	2,7	2,8	2,7	3,2	4,2	4,0

Hydrological Landscape: The Dobrichka River

Figure 1-4. Catchment area of Dobrichka River

The Dobrichka River, a right tributary of the Suhata River within the Danube River system, crosses the municipality. The river exhibits a distinctive flow pattern from a spring 278 meters above sea level in the "Kuza" locality. Before entering Dobrich city, its course is northward, forming an eastward bulging arc within the urban area.

The catchment area is asymmetrically configured, with a more developed left side (Figure 1-4). Its altitude ranges from 191–253 m (in the northern part) to 312–350 m. The steep slopes in the narrow upper drainage basin facilitate rapid surface runoff during intense rainfall. The river's hydrological regime is highly variable, with long dry periods and short flood events (Figure 1-5). The northern tributaries have two reservoirs.

Figure 1-5. Daily discharges of Suhata River 2000–2005

Population Dynamics of Dobrich City Municipality

The population of Dobrich has varied dramatically in the last 150 years, from 1872 to 2023 (Figure 6). The population increased between 1946 and 1992, reaching a peak of approximately 125,000 inhabitants. After 1992, the population steadily decreased to 87,361 by 2024.

Figure 1-6. Population Dynamics of Dobrich City Municipality

Economics of Dobrich City Municipality

Dobrich City Municipality is a significant modern industrial-agrarian and transportation center in Bulgaria's northeast region. The local economy includes food processing, which accounts for over 50% of the city's industrial output (production of dairy products, sausages, pasta, wines and spirits, non-alcoholic beverages; poultry meat products, flour, bread and pastry); light industry (production of men's and women's clothing, fur clothing, furniture and shoes); mechanical engineering (production of batteries, machinery and equipment for milk processing, semi-trailers and containers, agricultural machinery, radiators and filters for passenger and heavy-duty vehicles, plastic products). The local economy of the Dobrich Municipality is a dynamic system that combines agricultural heritage with modern economic practices.

The Dobrich City municipality boasts a rich cultural and historical heritage. It is home to the Architectural and Ethnographic Museum 'Old Dobrich', the Yordan Yovkov House Museum, the Yordan Yovkov Memorial House, the Military Cemetery Memorial Complex, the Art Gallery, the Nature and Animal Protection Center, the Saint Great Martyr George Church, the Holy Trinity Temple, the Beekeeping Exhibition 'Pchelomania', the 'Izida' Sports Complex, and other cultural landmarks. Dobrich hosts one of the largest agricultural exhibitions, 'Agriculture and Everything About It'.

Since 1990, September 25th has been celebrated as the city's holiday, marking the official commemoration of the 50th anniversary of Southern Dobrudzha's reunification with Bulgaria.

1.2 Main objectives of the project

The project ARCADIA aims to provide Dobrich municipality with a framework, tools, and support (methodological, financial, and technical) to assess its climate risks. It will allow the municipality to determine its vulnerabilities to extreme climate events and better prepare to address them. The project also helps the municipality strengthen its adaptation capacity and safeguard its economic stability and people. On the other hand, the project supports collaboration between local authorities, scientists, and stakeholders. CLIMAAX framework is very important for decision-making, as it is data-driven and aligned with European climate policies. The project will contribute to the long-term environmental and socio-economic stability of the Dobrich municipality.

The CLIMAAX framework provides the municipality of Dobrich with the following:

- ❖ understanding, assessing, and managing climate risk
- ❖ developing plans to mitigate extreme weather events' impact.
- ❖ to integrate climate adaptation strategy into urban and regional development plans.
- ❖ to prioritizing investments in resilient infrastructure and nature-based solutions.
- ❖ to facilitate collaboration between local authorities, scientists, businesses, and local communities.

1.3 Project team

The project team consists of the following positions and experts:

- Project manager responsible for overall project management, control and reporting functions - Pavel Pavlov - deputy mayor;
- Financial expert responsible for financial management and accounting - Petia Dimitrova;
- Environmental and climate expert for implementing and coordinating activities, drafting terms of reference, quality control of results - prof. Nelly Hristova;
- Municipal expert responsible for data collection, communication activities, coordination of information with external services - Miroslava Raynova.

The team was appointed by order of the mayor of the municipality, the environmental and climate expert was selected after conducting a public procurement procedure through a collection of offers with an invitation. The expert is professor in Climate, Atmosphere and Water Research Institute from the Bulgarian Academy of Science. A public procurement procedures will be carried out to support the municipality in the next stages of the project.

1.4 Outline of the document's structure

After the introduction to the background, the main objective of the project and the project team, this report explores three main thematic blocks: an initial assessment of climate risks for the municipality of Dobrich; conclusions based on the assessment, and a review of the progress and implementation of the next project phases.

The first block of climate risk assessment aims to define the scope of the climate risk assessment, examine the risks with the main hazards, exposures and vulnerabilities, analyse selected risk workflows from the CLIMAAX Handbook applied to the municipality and which hazard, exposure and vulnerability data are used. Based on the assessment, preliminary key findings from the risk assessment, incl. about severity, urgency, and availability of capacity will be drawn. In addition, preliminary monitoring and evaluation of the lessons learned in the first phase are presented, feedback received from stakeholders reported and potential other stakeholders identified.

The second block contains conclusions on climate risks reached at this stage of the project, as well as the main key findings.

The third block focuses on the assessment of progress and contribution to the implementation of future stages of the project, e.g. description of the relationship between the achieved results and the planned activities for the next stages with key performance indicators and objectives, and the actions taken to achieve them according to the project plan.

At the end of the report, supporting documentation and references are provided.

2 Climate risk assessment – phase 1

2.1 Scoping

2.1.1 Objectives

The main objective of the CRA is to contribute to strengthening the climate resilience of the Dobrich Municipality. The project will provide better understanding of the multiple climate risks and will increase the risk knowledge and awareness of the municipal administration, businesses and the general public. The CRA addresses the challenge of analysing the vulnerability of different social groups, the economic damages in different zones, and the development of specific adaptation measures. As a result, it will support a more informed decision-making, empowers the local community, and facilitates the development and implementation of robust climate adaptation policies and measures.

An example for such a policy for disaster prevention and reduction at the municipality is DRRP for the period 2026-2030 which is planned to be discussed and drafted in early 2026. This process provides a window of opportunity for the findings and recommendations of the CRA to be fed in the local decision-making. Based on the review of the legal, financial, and administrative framework, other policy documents could be identified and possibly informed by the outcomes of the project.

The limitations to the climate risk assessment identified for the flood hazard are lack of data on water protection and resolution of hydrological models (e.g., the hydrological models used to calculate flood heights may have limited resolution, which can lead to inaccuracies). Additionally, there is a problem with the accuracy of population data - the population estimate for 2025 is based on projections that may not accurately reflect the actual population density or distribution. There is a lack of data on the value of buildings. The economic damage is estimated based on JRC depth-damage functions, but without accurate data on the value of buildings in the area.

2.1.2 Context

Dobrich municipality is located in north-eastern Bulgaria. It is one of the few urban municipalities in Bulgaria. It is characterized by negative demographic and economic trends and it is vulnerable to climate hazards like floods, strong winds, snowstorms and icing. Especially devastating was the flood in 2014 which showed the vulnerability of the municipality to extreme climate events. Dobrich has competence in environmental and disaster protection by adopting local ordinances, plans and programs. A Disaster Protection plan was adopted in 2019, and in 2021 a municipal disaster risk reduction program (DRRP) 2021-2025 which partly addressed these vulnerabilities.

The major climate - related risks for Dobrich municipality are identified based on the experience and the analysis in the municipal integrated development plan for 2021-2027 according to which the main risks faced by the municipality are related to an increase in flood risks - the ravine of the Dobrichka river; severe droughts and related problems regarding the quantity and quality of water resources and the maintenance of green systems. These risks are a direct result of climate change and will have the most serious impact on industrial objects and systems; the green system of Dobrich; human health and water supply systems.

Dobrich municipality is especially vulnerable to flooding as a result of heavy rains or intense snowmelt. There are no dams built on the territory of the municipality, but only 4 km. east of the

municipality there are 2 micro-dams, which, in case of overflow or wall rupture could potentially endanger the city of Dobrich. According to the updated Preliminary Flood Risk Assessment in the Danube Region (2022-2027) under the Floods Directive, the city of Dobrich is designated as an area with a significant potential risk of floods. In the Dobrich region, the roads very often become impassable in the winter as a result of heavy snowfall and winds and therefore the citizens are advised to not take trips on these routes during heavy snowfalls and winds.

The municipality adopted a DRRP on the territory of the Dobrich Municipality for the period 2021 - 2025 and a Disaster Protection plan in 2019. The plan sets the highest level of risk for floods and earthquakes, and the DRRP provides for reducing the risk of floods through the construction of hydrological facilities, early warning systems for high water levels, video surveillance along the Dobrichka River, good spatial planning of the territory and last but not least - increasing readiness to prevent or reduce the negative consequences of floods through preventive measures, training of the population, adequate preparation, planning of rescue activities, etc. As an extremely necessary preventive measure, the annual cleaning of the Dobrichka River bed and ravines and their maintenance in conditions ensuring water conductivity is applied.

As regards to the river flood hazard, according to the updated Preliminary Flood Risk Assessment (PFRA) in the Danube Region (2022-2027) under the Floods Directive, the city of Dobrich has been designated as an Area of Significant Potential for Flood Risk (ASPFR 2019) with code BG1_APSFR_DB100: Dobrich River - Dobrich City. The area encompasses the Dobrichka River and two of its right tributaries - Serdika Gorge and an unnamed gorge flowing through the Northern Industrial Zone. The flood types, according to the source, are: river, flash flood, urban flood (Dobrich City). The defined flood types for mapping the threat and risk of floods under the FD are:

- River floods - along the Dobrich River and Serdika Gorge;
- Rain-sudden (torrible) floods – along the nameless right tributary of the Dobrich River, flowing through the Northern Industrial Zone of the city;
- Rain-urban – northern part of the city of Dobrich (North 2 residential area and Northern Industrial Zone).

The following risk assessment by indicators have been identified: human health - significant risk, real estate - significant risk, infrastructure - significant risk, economic activity from the secondary and tertiary sectors - significant risk, expert assessment - significant risk.

The risk has been identified in the Environmental Protection Program of the Municipality of Dobrich for the period 2021-2027 (EPP). Flood risk management is priority 3, from Specific Strategic Objective 2 "Maintaining the good status of surface and groundwater and optimizing the quality of services in the field of water management" of the program. The EPP action plan provides for action measures and performance indicators.

In the immediate vicinity of the Dobrichka riverbed and its tributaries, two large commercial sites, a commercial park and hardware stores, as well as one hotel and one restaurant, have been built. Climate change leads to the risk of sudden, intense, torrential rains, resulting in local flooding and the possibility of flooding of sites in the field of trade and services.

Against this background, the municipality has limited capacity for implementation of climate adaptation or disaster protection measures and its budget has not provided so far for specific climate resilience measures or investments. These limitations will be relieved if projects like

ARKADIA provide analysis of the multiple climate risks and increase the knowledge and awareness of the municipal administration, businesses and general public. In this respect, very important planning instrument is the Integrated Development Plan (IDP) of Dobrich municipality which determines the regional and spatial development of the municipal territory, outlines the current problems, needs and potential for development of the region, medium-term goals and priorities.

2.1.3 Participation and risk ownership

Two main groups may be affected by flooding, as was seen in 2014, as they are located in the path of the river - firstly, these are neighborhoods inhabited by a socially disadvantaged population, which builds illegal structures along the river, and secondly, these are local small and medium-sized enterprises located in the northern industrial zone, also built in the intended flood zone of the river. Another vulnerable area is the old quarter of the city, completely built up with houses, which is in the lower part of the city and where there are the relevant educational and health institutions, which may suffer.

The ownership of various risks that may affect the population of the city of Dobrich is regulated by a number of planning and strategic documents adopted by the Municipal Council, such as:

- Disaster Risk Reduction Program (DRRP) on the territory of the Municipality of Dobrich for the period 2021 - 2025
- Disaster Protection Plan of the Municipality of Dobrich from 2019
- Plan for evacuation and/or dispersal in the event of a disaster of the population, animals and material values from the Municipality of Dobrich - 2015;

The key stakeholders for the project include

Competent authorities: the municipal administration and council of Dobrich Municipality, the Regional Directorate for Fire Safety and Protection of the Population; Regional Environment and Water Inspectorate; the National Institute of Metrology and Hydrology; Regional Directorate of Forestry; Regional Health Inspectorate; Danube River Basin Directorate; Water Supply and Sanitation entity.

Community Members: Residents, community leaders, local NGOs, universities in the region and professional high schools.

Businesses and Industry: Private sector entities, including businesses, industries of properties exposed to floods or exposed to the snow and ice accumulation in the winter and the risk of accidents and road closures.

Vulnerable population, including low-income communities, marginalized groups who are often disproportionately affected by climate change impacts with special attention to the vulnerable groups living in low-lying areas with inadequate drainage exposed to flooding, residents in periphery areas where housing structures who may be less resistant to strong winds, commuters exposed to the snow and ice accumulation in the winter and the risk of accidents and road closures.

The project activities designed to communicate the outputs contributed to the visibility of the project before the journalists and the general public. A press conference took place on January 23, 2025 and it was covered by the local media and publications on the municipality's website. The first meeting with stakeholders to present the report on the implementation and adaptation of climate change risk assessment tools was held on March 28, 2025. Participants in the event were representatives of the Dobrich Municipality, the Dobrich rural municipality, Regional Administration, Regional Information Center - Dobrich, Fire Safety and Population Protection Agency, representatives of NGOs.

2.2 Risk Exploration

2.2.1 Screen risks (selection of main hazards)

The climate hazards and potential climate risks for the Dobrich Municipality are as follows:

- Intense rainfall and flooding, which lead to street flooding and infrastructure damage.
- Heat waves (temperatures above 35 °C) in the summer months are risky for older people, children, and people with chronic conditions.
- Storms and strong winds: Stormy northeast winds cause material damage, fallen trees, and transportation disruptions.
- Ice storms and heavy snowfall: Ice and snow accumulation disrupt roads and power supply.
- Drought (meteorological and hydrological), which affects agriculture and water resources.

The current situation in Dobrich Municipality is the following:

1. Heat waves increase and affect the health of the residents and crops that cannot withstand high temperatures.
2. Droughts appear in the summer.
3. Intense rainfall and flooding are risks for infrastructure and transport, as well as erosion and crop damage.
4. Storms and strong winds are typically for autumn and winter, causing damage to infrastructure and outdoor objects, such as roofs, trees, and electric poles.
5. Hailstorms – periodically occurring in spring and summer mainly affect agriculture, destroying fruits and vegetables.

Where does the hazard occur?

The greatest risk of flooding comes from the Dobricka River's riverbed and dams, which periodically overflow their banks. Urban areas are also vulnerable, especially during heavy rainfall and flooding, typical for peripheral areas with poor drainage systems.

Who is affected?

The most affected are the residents (especially older adults, children, and people with chronic diseases) during heat waves, the infrastructure (buildings, roads, and facilities) during floods and storms, and the public services during droughts.

The hazards are observed/expected in the area of Dobrich municipality are flooding, strong winds, heat waves, and droughts have been observed in the region. According to forecast data, the intensity of these hazards is expected to increase in the future. Accordingly, the hazards will you cover in the risk assessment are river flooding, heavy rainfall; urban heatwaves, heavy snow, blizzards and windstorms.

The project will apply the experience of the experts in assessing flood risks, especially those caused by intense rainfall. The assessment will include historical data on past events and preliminary evaluations of Dobrich's city's vulnerability to flooding. Additional data from hydrometeorological monitoring (from the National Institute of Meteorology and Hydrology, Bulgaria), such as daily temperature, precipitation, snow and snow cover, wind speed, and daily discharges (for the Dobrichka River) will be needed.

2.2.2 Workflow selection

2.2.2.1 Workflow #1 Floods:

- *Main Processes:*
 - Collecting historical flood data and hydrometeorological monitoring.
 - Mapping of flood-prone areas based on topography, drainage capacity, and precipitation trends.
 - Assessment of infrastructure vulnerability, including roads, buildings, and drainage systems.
 - Identification of emergency response measures and flood mitigation strategies.
- *Vulnerable Groups and Exposed Areas:*
 - Urban populations in low-lying areas with inadequate drainage.
 - Public infrastructure, including transportation networks and water supply systems.

2.2.2.2 Workflow #2 Strong Wind

- *Main Processes:*
 - Analysis of wind speed and storm occurrence data.
 - Assessment of building and infrastructure resistance to strong winds.
 - Identification of risk zones where wind damage is more frequent (e.g., open fields, coastal areas).
 - Implementation of preventive measures, such as strengthening buildings and planting windbreaks.
- *Vulnerable Groups and Exposed Areas:*
 - Residents in periphery areas where housing structures may be less resistant to strong winds.
 - Public services and critical infrastructure, such as power lines, roads, and emergency response facilities.

- Forests and green spaces, which are susceptible to tree damage and increased fire risk due to fallen branches.

2.2.2.3 Workflow #3 Snow

- *Main Processes:*
 - Monitoring snow accumulation, snowmelt rates, and temperature variations to assess the risk of rapid thawing and related hazards.
 - Evaluating the impact of heavy snowfall on transportation, infrastructure, and public services.
 - Assessing the risks of snowmelt-induced flooding, particularly in areas with poor drainage or near rivers and low-lying regions.
 - Identifying critical infrastructure vulnerabilities, such as power lines, roads, and buildings, that may be affected by heavy snow loads and ice formation.
- *Vulnerable Groups and Exposed Areas:*
 - Commuters and transportation services, as snow and ice accumulation increase the risk of accidents and road closures.
 - Public infrastructure and utilities, including power grids, communication networks, and heating systems.

2.2.3 Choose Scenario

For Dobrich municipality, several scenario assumptions are relevant when assessing climate risk, considering both climate change impacts and socio-economic developments over different timeframes:

Short-term (Next 5 Years)

Increase in extreme weather events: More frequent heavy rainfall, leading to localized flooding, particularly in urban areas with insufficient drainage. Short-term droughts and heatwaves affect the local economy. Rising maintenance costs due to more intense weather fluctuations (e.g., increased energy demand for cooling during heat waves). Slow implementation of climate adaptation strategies, despite awareness of risks.

Medium-Term (20-30 Years)

Rising temperatures and prolonged dry periods could lead to more severe drought conditions, stressing water resources. Changes in land use and economic activities: Possible diversification of agriculture towards drought-resistant crops; expansion of water-efficient irrigation techniques. Population growth may increase housing, water, and energy demand, creating new vulnerabilities.

Long-Term (50-100 Years)

If global warming continues, extreme heat and prolonged droughts may drastically alter water availability, requiring structural adaptation of the local economy and infrastructure. Population decline due to aging and migration trends, possibly leading to a reduced workforce and economic development. Groundwater depletion and increased temperatures could make long-term water availability a critical issue.

Relevant Scenarios for Dobrich from the Workflows

Several scenarios available in the risk workflows are beneficial for assessing and managing climate-related risks in the region of Dobrich:

1. Heatwaves and Drought Risk Scenario

Relevance: Dobrich is already experiencing rising temperatures and prolonged dry periods, leading to water scarcity and agricultural stress. Usefulness: This scenario helps evaluate future water availability, irrigation needs, and adaptation strategies for agriculture, infrastructure, and public health.

2. Flood Risk Scenario

Relevance: Intense rainfall events are becoming more frequent, increasing the risk of urban flooding and river overflow. Usefulness: This scenario supports early warning systems, improved drainage planning, and land-use policies to mitigate flood damage.

3. Windstorm and Extreme Weather Scenario

Relevance: Strong winds and storms have impacted the region, affecting infrastructure, transportation, and energy supply. Usefulness: This scenario helps reinforce buildings, update emergency preparedness plans, and protect critical infrastructure from storm damage.

By integrating these scenarios into climate risk assessment, Dobrich can develop targeted adaptation measures, strengthen resilience, and minimize economic losses due to climate-related hazards.

2.3 Risk Analysis

2.3.1 Workflow #1 Floods

The flood risk assessment in the Municipality of Dobrich City follows the workflows outlined in the CLIMAAX Handbook. It includes the following steps:

- Hazard assessment utilizes models that define flood depths for the 10-year and 500-year scenarios and two climate models - RCP4.5 and RCP8.5.
- The exposure of the population and buildings was evaluated using data on population distribution and built-up areas.
- The vulnerability is based on economic damages (46.15 million EUR annually) and the number of affected and evacuated people (700–900 individuals).

Finally, the climate risk was calculated as a combination of hazard, exposure, and vulnerability in the central parts of Dobrich, which have higher population and building density.

Table 2-1 Data overview workflow #1

<i>Hazard data</i>	<i>Vulnerability data</i>	<i>Exposure data</i>	<i>Risk output</i>
Flood Depth Data	Economic Damage Estimates Evacuation Estimates Vulnerability Table	Population Distribution Building Distribution Exposure Graph Exposure Table	Climate Risk Assessment Affected Areas Risk Assessment Table
...	...		

2.3.1.1 Hazard assessment

The provided maps give the following flood hazard levels in the municipality of Dobrich City:

10-year return period: The flood hazard for the 10-year return period in Dobrich is characterized by a maximum depth of 5-6 meters, following the Dobrichka River. The water affects part of the industrial zone "Sever" and part of the residential buildings. Because the frequency of this flood is 2 (Moderate), and the Intensity is also 2 (Moderate), the overall hazard assessment is 2 (Moderate to High).

50-year return period. The flood with an annual probability of 2% (1 in 50 years) in Dobrich has a maximum depth of 6-7 meters and more extensive coverage than the 10-year scenario. The water is more symmetrical and distributed near the riverbanks. The hazard rating for frequency is 1 (Low), for intensity: 2-3 (Moderate to High), and for the overall hazard: 2-3 (Moderate to High).

100-year return period. The flood hazard for the 100-year return period in Dobrich is characterised by a lower frequency, with a higher potential for severe water accumulation (maximum depth of 7-8 meters) and significantly expanded coverage compared to the 50-year scenario. The ratings for frequency are 1 (Low), for the intensity is 3 (High), and for the overall hazard rating is 3 (High).

500-year return period. The flood with an annual probability of 1 in 500 years in Dobrich has a maximum depth of 8-9 meters, flooding the comprehensive central urban area and the industrial zone "Sever." This is an infrequent flood event characterized by extreme water depths and a potential for infrastructure damage. The ratings for frequency are 1 (Low), for the intensity is 3 (High), and for the overall hazard rating is 3 (High).

2.3.1.2 Risk assessment

10-year period: Hazard (2) × Exposure (2) × Vulnerability (2) = 8 Risk: Moderate to high (8/27)
 50-year period: Hazard (2) × Exposure (2) × Vulnerability (2) = 8 Risk: Moderate to high (8/27)
 100-year period: Hazard (3) × Exposure (2-3) × Vulnerability (2-3) = 12-27 Risk: High (12-27/27)
 500-year period: Hazard (3) × Exposure (3) × Vulnerability (3) = 27 Risk: Maximum (27/27)

See Annex 1 for the Flood Risk Assessment

2.4 Preliminary Key Risk Assessment Findings

2.4.1 Severity

The Municipality of Dobrich City flood risk analysis revealed the following findings.

Flood depths for the 10-year return period scenario vary from 6–8 m in the central areas to 0–2 m in the periphery, while the 500-year return period (500-yr) scenario shows depths of 7–9 m in the centre and 1–3 m in the periphery. Exposure is significant, with 9,344 individuals (10.7% of the population) exposed in the 10-year scenario and 12,290 (14.1%) in the 500-year scenario. Vulnerability is high due to economic damages averaging 46.15 million EUR annually, with per-building damages of 6–12 million EUR and a low number of evacuees (700 for 10 years, 900 for 500 years), indicating gaps in evacuation planning. The climate risk is medium to high for the population (rated 2–3) and high for buildings in the 10-year scenario (rated 3).

River floods in Dobrich are a severe climate risk. Historically, the Dobrich has experienced flooding events, though specific data on past events were unavailable for this analysis. Based on hydrological models, current trends indicate that even a 10-year flood event (10% annual probability) can result in depths of up to 8 m in the city centre, affecting 9,344 individuals and causing economic damages of 46.15 million EUR annually. The potential impacts are significant: central areas, with high population density (15–20 people per 3-arcsecond cell, approximately 90 m × 66–69 m) and dense building stock, face the highest risk. The severity increases in a 500-year scenario when the flood will affect 12,290 individuals.

The flooding poses a severe climate risk for Dobrich. The current models reveal significant hazard across different return periods.

2.4.2 Urgency

Flooding impacts people and infrastructure in Dobrich most when an early warning system is not activated. Several preliminary actions are needed to minimize damage: riverbed corrections, modernization of drainage facilities, and better preparedness of people to respond to such disasters. The modelled risk does not explain how this hazard appears: slow or sudden. The lack of information on slow or fast-onset hazards does not affect the urgency assessment.

2.4.3 Capacity

Flood risk reduction is carried out primarily through the construction of hydrotechnical facilities, early warning systems for high water levels, video surveillance along the Dobrichka River, good spatial planning of the territory and, last but not least, increasing readiness to prevent or reduce the negative consequences of floods through preventive measures, education of the population, adequate preparation, planning of rescue activities, etc. As an extremely necessary preventive measure, the annual cleaning of the Dobrichka River bed and ravines and their maintenance in conditions ensuring water conductivity is applied.

There are a lot of opportunities to deal with flood risk in the Municipality of Dobrich City. Some of them are listed below:

Financial Opportunities. Reducing flood damage can attract funding (national and EU) and lower insurance premiums for residents and businesses. Sustainable drainage systems, retention basins, and river restoration projects can generate jobs and stimulate local businesses.

Social Opportunities. Early warning systems, awareness campaigns, and encouraging participation in local decision-making will improve disaster preparedness, encourage public engagement, and reduce stress and displacement.

Human Capital. Dealing with flood risk in the municipality can build capacity among local authorities, engineers, and emergency responders; facilitate knowledge transfer and training; and enhance local expertise in hydrology, urban planning, and climate adaptation.

Physical aspects. Dealing with flood risk in the municipality of Dobrich will positively affect urban planning and overall urban resilience. It can modernize municipal infrastructure (by using digital tools for flood monitoring, such as real-time sensors).

Natural aspects. There are several opportunities that may emerge from dealing with the floods: enhancing biodiversity by ecosystem restoration, supporting groundwater recharge, new permeable surfaces, forestation, green roofs.

Conclusion: Dealing with floods in the Municipality of Dobrich area can lead to financial investments, stronger social cohesion, improved infrastructure, enhanced local expertise, and environmental benefits. These opportunities allow the municipality to build a more resilient and sustainable future.

2.5 Preliminary Monitoring and Evaluation

Floods are a significant climate hazard in Dobrich. Historically, the municipality's most significant flood was in June 2014, when intense rainfall caused considerable damage to infrastructure and residential buildings. The data confirms that there is a risk of catastrophic flooding in Dobrich. The vulnerable areas are part of the central and the industrial zone "Sever" (North).

It was established that there are limitations of local hydrometeorological data – there is no detailed information on the daily water volumes of the Dobrich River. There is also a lack of historical information on previous floods, making preparing long-term models and scenarios challenging.

The municipal administration expressed concern that the current infrastructure is not sufficiently resilient to extreme rainfall events and that investments in expanding the drainage system are needed. Firefighters found inaccuracies in the floodplain area for a 1-in-500-year flood. Experts in hydrology and urban planning suggested exploring the possibilities of widening the riverbed and building buffer zones.

For the future stages of the project the cooperation with the National Institute of Meteorology and Hydrology (NIMH) will be needed to provide more detailed hydrological and climate data. Financial and insurance institutions can contribute data on the economic damage caused by floods. At this stage, we primarily rely on existing hydrometeorological data from the National Institute of Meteorology and Hydrology (NIMH) and past flood event reports, particularly about the June 2014 flood in Dobrich. Additional data are required to improve the accuracy of flood risk assessment in Dobrich: more detailed hydrological and heavy rainfall data (from NIMH), more granular land use and infrastructure data, and a demographic profile of the Dobrich population (vulnerable populations, etc.). Incorporating the risk assessment (GIS-based flood mapping) into municipal planning would be good.

The citizens can share their needs after a flood through surveys and public discussions. It will be beneficial to involve and consult local NGOs and active citizens with interest and experience in environmental protection to get even wider public legitimacy of the project's outputs.

A new DRRP will be drafted in 2026 and the findings and recommendations of this climate risk assessment could be applied for more detailed and science- and fact-based decision-making.

3. Conclusions Phase 1- Climate risk assessment

Main conclusions

An increase in risk is found with increasing return period, which is expressed in an increase in flood depth and extent. The threatened areas are concentrated around the Dobrich River and the low-lying urban areas of Dobrich, where a high concentration of residential, commercial and industrial buildings, as well as critical infrastructure, is observed.

The 10-year and 500-year flood scenarios show a significant increase in flood depth and extent, as well as increasing (exponentially) economic damage (from 60 to 100 million euros) and the number of population exposed to danger (from 9,300 to 12,290 people) and evacuations (from 700 to 900 people).

The first phase of the climate risk assessment focused on:

1. River flood hazards with different return periods in Dobrich Municipality. Flood maps for different return periods, such as 10-year, 50-year, 100-year, and 500-year, were collected. More real-time hydrological monitoring is needed to improve the accuracy of flood risk assessments, especially for short-term forecasting.
 2. An assessment of the depth and extent of river flooding in the municipality was made. Integrated flood and building maps allowed a better understanding of the exposure of residential and industrial areas (North zone), and vulnerable areas were delineated. Maps, tables, and graphs provide specific information on economic damage and the population that will be evacuated during floods of different return periods.
 3. The existing institutional and technical capacity to cope with a changing climate was studied and presented, which will help identify strengths and gaps in current adaptation strategies.
- challenges not addressed

A detailed quantitative assessment of potential economic losses has not been developed due to limited data and uncertainty in forecasting models.

The impact of flooding on different social groups, especially vulnerable communities, has not been differentiated.

Specific flood mitigation strategies have not been developed, which requires further exploration of potential solutions.

4. Progress evaluation and contribution to future phases

Table 4-1 Overview key performance indicators

Key performance indicators	Progress
1 report on the application and adaptation of the CLIMAAX framework published	Submitted.
5000 residents, key local and regional authorities, and stakeholders reached through local and national media, incl. social media channels. (accumulative, by the end of the project)	To date, more than 100 individuals, key local and regional authorities and stakeholders, have attended the project's kick-off events, as well as more than 215 others reached out through local and national media, and 150 visitors through social media channels.
<i>Kick-off meeting</i>	The kick-off meeting took place after selection of all team members and the issuance of a mayor's order in January 2025. At the event, the project and team members were presented to representatives of regional and municipal administrations, as well as to other institutions related to climate change and the risks to society that it leads to.
<i>1 workshop with stakeholders</i>	The workshop presentation of the report to municipal officials, representatives of other administrations, who were previously familiarized with the report and participated in a discussion on the results of the application of the methodological framework. /and non-governmental organizations related to climate change and the risks to society that it leads to. In the process of work, feedback was received through a pre-prepared survey.
<i>At least 5 local or national NGOs and 20 local community members involved in the workshops with stakeholders</i>	In process of implementation.

Milestones	Progress
M1 <i>Kick-off meeting of the project team with municipal and external experts</i>	The kick-off meeting took place after the election of all team members and the issuance of a mayor's order in January 2025. At the event, the project and team members were presented to representatives of regional and municipal administrations, as well as to other institutions related to climate change and the risks to society that it leads to.
M2: Press conference to announce the project and its goals	The media presentation of the project took place a week after the team's kick-off meeting. The event was broadcast in real time on one of the local electronic media outlets, and after the event, publications were made in four such outlets, one regional print publication, as well as on the municipality's website.
M3: Completion of the workshop on the application and adaptation of the CLIMAAX framework	The workshop consisted of a presentation of the report to municipal officials, representatives of other administrations, and participated in a discussion on the results of the application of the methodological framework.

Table 4-2 Overview milestones

5. Supporting documentation

- [Annex 1 Flood Risk Assessment](#)
- https://pronewsdobrich.bg/analiz-na-riska-za-dobrich-ot-klimatichnite-promeni-predstoi-da-se-izvarshi-po-proekt-p557351?fbclid=IwY2xjawlIZoJleHRuA2FlbQlXMAABHTer9Hi_d-fYG3UH-r2kmCZ4KvW-fQcL-VUxenlCcYHjniY8q4EDhclimA_aem_uWFPCeulC0NUXpwUf2SkeA
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